

Some Acid Constituents of Jute Fibre.

By J. K. CROWDRURY AND M. N. MITRA.

The presence of acid substances in jute fibre may be surmised from the wellknown fact that in dyeing, jute behaves like a tanned fibre and has direct affinity for basic dyes. This surmise receives further support from the fact that when boiled with 12 per cent. hydrochloric acid, jute fibre evolves considerable amount of carbon dioxide, indicating the presence of acids belonging to the "uronic" group. The present investigations were undertaken with a view to isolate and identify the various acidic substances that might be present in jute and as a result galacturonic, glycuronic and pectic acids have been found present in the fibre.

The separation and isolation of glycuronic and galacturonic acids are particularly difficult when they occur side by side in any substance. Glycuronic acid has been separated by us from the major part of galacturonic acid by taking advantage of the easy oxidisability of the latter by means of air, while galacturonic acid has been separated from glycuronic acid through the barium salt.

Unlike glycuronic acid, galacturonic acid could not be obtained in crystalline form. Both these uronic acids yielded carbon dioxide and furfural when treated with 12 per cent. hydrochloric acid. The carbonic acid and furfural values served as a means for their characterisation. Both reduced Fehling's solution and responded to Mohlisch test. On boiling with 2.5 per cent. sulphuric acid, decarboxylation took place and glycuronic acid yielded xylose while galacturonic acid yielded arabinose. Bromine water oxidised the former to saccharic acid and the latter to mucic acid. Both formed cinchonine salt which served as a means for their identification.

Crude pectin extracted from jute with 5 per cent. ammonium oxalate was purified and then converted into free pectic acid by the method of Candlin and Schryver (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1928, **B**, 103, 367).

Unlike the pectic acid from onion and citrus as obtained by the above workers, the pectic acid from jute was found to give colloidal solution with water and had, therefore, to be precipitated from its ammonium salt by alcohol acidulated with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The yield was 2.18 per cent. (calculated on delignified jute).

The pectic acid, thus obtained, was a very light, absolutely white amorphous powder and gave insoluble salts of heavy metals. It became greyish black at 195.97° and melted with decomposition at 233.35°. It was found insoluble in almost all the usual organic solvents. When heated with acid and alkali decarboxylation and hydrolysis took place. This was evidently the reason that it could not be detected in the ammonium extract from which the uronic acids were isolated. On heating with dilute acid (1 N-sulphuric acid), hydrolysis without any decarboxylation took place but when boiled with 7.5 per cent. sulphuric acid, hydrolysis and decarboxylation proceeded simultaneously and 15.81 per cent. galactose was found in the products of hydrolysis.

Special mention may here be made of the furfural value of the uronic acids. Nanji, Paton and Ling (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1925., **44**, 253r) mention 33 per cent. as the furfural value of these uronic acids while Norman (*Biochem. J.*, 1929, **23**, 1353) gives 16.66 per cent. as the furfural value of uronic anhydride. None of the investigators have, however, furnished any experimental data in support of these figures. The furfural value of glycuronic acid has been determined by us and found to be 21.84 per cent. This figure is in fair agreement with that of galacturonic acid (19.96 p.c.) determined by Ehrlich and Schubert (*Ber.*, 1929, **62**, 2012). It is evidently incorrect to estimate the pentoses in plant products from the furfural value alone, a part of which must be attributed to the uronic acids. In the light of the present determination of the furfural value of uronic acids as 21.84 per cent., it will be seen that about 1/5th of the total furfural yield of jute fibre must be attributed to the presence of these acids and only the rest to pentosans.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Delignification of jute fibre was carried out by chlorine peroxide gas in large soda-lime towers with ground glass joints. The fibre was, however, previously boiled with 0.5 per cent. caustic soda solution

for 1 hour in order to facilitate the removal of lignin. The analytical data of the raw and delignified jute are given below.

	Raw jute. (%).	Delignified jute (%).
Lignin	12.74	Nil
α -cellulose		5.82
Ash	0.605	
Fat & resin	0.585	Nil
Furfural	11.503	10.894 (calc. on raw jute)
Uronic acids	10.824	10.924 (,, ,,)

Extraction with ammonium hydroxide.—The delignified fibre was extracted with 17 per cent. ammonium hydroxide for 6 hours at a stretch at 45°. The excess of ammonia was driven off from the brown extract at a low temperature. It was found that about three extractions were necessary to make the fibre free from uronic carbon dioxide.

Isolation of glycuronic acid.—A portion of the extract was treated with basic lead acetate when a yellowish precipitate was obtained which was washed free from lead. This was suspended in water and decomposed with sulphuretted hydrogen. Considerable difficulties were experienced in removing the precipitate of lead sulphide owing to its colloidal nature. Precipitation was, however, facilitated by the addition of a little alcohol to the filtrate which had been previously freed from the sulphide as far as possible. The filtrate was decolourised with animal charcoal and concentrated under reduced pressure (15 mm.), a slow current of air being passed through a capillary during evaporation. After a time, white precipitates began to separate out and the syrup was poured in excess of alcohol when a white precipitate was thrown down. It was filtered, washed with alcohol and dried. A part of this substance was found soluble in cold water giving an opalescent solution while the residue, crystallised from hot water, yielded crystals of mucic acid. The opalescence of the solution could be removed with a few drops of acetic acid. It was concentrated under reduced pressure and poured to excess of alcohol. The precipitate was further purified by repeated solution and precipitation and was found to have properties similar to those of glycogen. The alcoholic filtrate.

after precipitation of mucic acid and glycogen, was concentrated in vacuum and left in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid for 2—3 days, when white crystalline needles of glycuronic acid were obtained.

The following tests served to identify and characterise the above mentioned products.

Glycuronic acid melted at 159.61°. The cinchonine salt was prepared by adding a concentrated solution of cinchonine in 96 per cent. alcohol to a 2 per cent. alcoholic solution of glycuronic acid. Crystals were obtained on concentration and standing overnight and were recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 199-200°. Glycuronic acid yielded 21.84 per cent. furfural as determined by the phloroglucide method. Nitrogen found in the cinchonine salt was 6.03 per cent. (theoretical, 5.74 per cent.). The acid reduced Fehling's solution, turned yellow with caustic soda and responded to the Mohlish test with α -naphthol. Decarboxylation of the acid was effected as follows:

The acid (about 1g.) was boiled with sulphuric acid (180 c.c., 2.5 p. c.) for 3 hours under reflux. The excess of sulphuric acid was removed with powdered barium carbonate and the filtrate was concentrated to a syrup in vacuum. The presence of xylose in the syrup was established by Tollens' Orcinol test and by means of Bertrand's reagent.

Mucic acid as obtained above melted at 214° and the silver salt gave Ag, 6.03 per cent. The tetraacetyl derivative melted at 262-63°.

Glycogen, a white amorphous powder formed an opalescent solution in water, the opalescence being removable by a few drops of acetic acid. Iodine gave a reddish brown coloration which disappeared on heating and reappeared on cooling. It formed insoluble precipitate with basic lead acetate and turned slightly yellow on prolonged exposure to air. Hydrolysis with dilute hydrochloric acid yielded glucose, which was identified by Barfoed's and Nylander's reagents.

Isolation of galacturonic acid.—The delignified fibre was extracted with ammonium hydroxide (5 per cent.) under the same conditions as described before and the extract was freed from ammonia at a low temperature (45°). On the addition of barium hydroxide, the barium salt of glycuronic acid separated out and was washed free from baryta and then decomposed with sulphuric acid, the excess being removed with powdered barium carbonate. The filtrate was

concentrated under reduced pressure. On pouring the resulting syrup in alcohol, a small quantity of mucic acid separated as before while the alcoholic filtrate yielded traces of glycuronic acid.

The mother liquor after separation of barium glycuronate was freed from excess of baryta with carbonic acid gas, was concentrated under reduced pressure and poured in excess of alcohol when the pale yellow precipitate of barium galacturonate separated out. It was decomposed with sulphuric acid, excess of which was removed with barium carbonate and the filtrate was concentrated in vacuum.

The *syrup* thus obtained reduced Fehling's solution. The cinchonine salt was prepared by treating the barium salt with cinchonine sulphate, the filtrate being concentrated in vacuum and allowed to crystallise. The cinchonine salt was finally obtained in the form of fine white needles after recrystallisation from alcohol, m.p. 155-58°. Nitrogen found in the cinchonine salt was 5.97 per cent. (theoretical, 5.74 per cent.). Decarboxylation of the acid was carried out in the same way as that of glycuronic acid and arabinose was detected in the products of hydrolysis by Tollen's Orcinol test and was confirmed by means of the *p*-bromophenylhydrazone, m.p. 152°.

Isolation of pectic acid.—Delignified jute was extracted with 0.5 per cent. ammonium oxalate at 85-90° until the residual fibre was free from uronic carbon dioxide. The pale yellow extract was concentrated to a small volume and poured in excess of alcohol when a pale yellow gelatinous precipitate slowly separated out. After standing for 24 hours, it was filtered and washed with graded strengths of alcohol and finally with ether. By repeated solution in water and precipitation with alcohol, it was obtained as an almost white gel. To a solution of this pectin in water, an equal volume of saturated lime water was added and the mixture was allowed to stand overnight. The white gel of calcium pectate was treated with a warm solution of ammonium oxalate (2 p. c.), the precipitate of calcium oxalate being filtered off. The clear solution of ammonium pectate was then treated with a large excess of alcohol acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid and allowed to stand for 24 hours. The white gel of pectic acid thus obtained was washed repeatedly with graded strengths of alcohol, then with ether and finally dried in vacuum. The yield was approximately 2.2 per cent. calculated on delignified fibre. Analysis of this pectic acid yielded ash, 0.066; furfural, 28.1; uronic CO₂, 17.45 and Ag (silver salt), 28.4 per cent.

It may be noted that the above uronic carbon dioxide is equivalent to 69.8 per cent. uronic acid and 98.77 per cent. pectic acid (Nanji, Paton and Ling, *loc. cit.*).

Hydrolysis of pectic acid.—The substance (about 7.5 g.) was treated with 1N- H_2SO_4 (300 c.c.) under reflux for 3 hours at 125-30°. The excess of sulphuric acid was removed with barium carbonate and the filtrate, concentrated to a syrup, was poured in 20 per cent. alcohol. The precipitate thus separated was found to be barium galacturonate, while arabinose and galactose were found in the alcoholic filtrate.

Hydrolysis was next conducted with 2.5 per cent. H_2SO_4 in the manner described above. In this case only arabinose and galactose were found in the products of hydrolysis, galacturonic acid being evidently decarboxylated in the course of hydrolysis. 15.81 per cent. galactose was found in the pectic acid as estimated by the mucic acid method. It is evident that for the identification and estimation of galactose by oxidation to mucic acid, all traces of galacturonic acid must be removed. This was effected by taking advantage of the complete insolubility of the barium salt in 80 per cent. alcohol.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
DACCA UNIVERSITY.

Received May 9, 1932.